

SHORT NOTES

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES ON MERCURY MOLYBDATE

BY C. M. GUPTA AND RAM SAHAI SAXENA

A survey of literature reveals that there are meagre references on the study of mercury molybdate. Molybdate ion exists in different states of aggregation depending on the p_H of the solution (Jander *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1930, 194, 383). It is of interest therefore to study the conditions favourable for the precipitation of mercury molybdate by applying electrometric methods.

'AnalaR' (B.D.H.) chemicals were used. Na_2MoO_4 solution was estimated as $\text{MoS}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 9, 263) and $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ was prepared in the minimum amount of HNO_3 (dil.) and was estimated as $[\text{Hg}(\text{CNS})_2]$ by titrating against standardised KCNS (Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Analysis", p. 265).

For measurement of E.M.F., Cambridge p_H -meter was used. A bright platinum wire was used as an indicator electrode in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode. Titrations were done in aqueous and aqueous-alcoholic solutions. Titrations in presence of alcohol were carried out up to a total concentration of 20% by volume. Curves were plotted between the volume of the titrant and the E.M.F. observed. From the sharp jump in the potential, indicated by the titration curve, the end-point could be found out. Mercury nitrate and sodium molybdate were alternately used as the titre, and the titrant was added through a micro-burette. p_H of the solutions was measured using glass electrode of the range 1-13 p_H .

The p_H of Na_2MoO_4 was 7.2 and that of $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, 1.3. Dilute solutions used in these experiments were of p_H 2. The molybdate ion is said to exist in the following state of aggregation at different p_H of the solution :

All the above ionic species are p_H -reversible. The change from one to another is never sudden. They are supposed to exist in equilibrium. According to Raman Rao (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 13B, 739) Ca, Ba, Sr and Cd molybdates are precipitated at p_H 4.18 and below this p_H , no precipitation takes place. But in this case at p_H 2, normal mercury molybdate was precipitated, having the composition $\text{HgO} \cdot \text{MoO}_3$. The compound on analysis for the molybdate and Mo content gave also the same composition as obtained by potentiometric method. When Na_2MoO_4 is added to $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and the reverse, and the potential between the platinum indicator electrode and saturated calomel electrode is measured and plotted against the volume of the titrant added, a sharp jump in potential is observed at the end-point, corresponding to the formation and precipitation of mercury molybdate, $\text{HgO} \cdot \text{MoO}_3$.

The curves are symmetrical on both sides of the equivalence point and the results are concordant and accurate. The addition of alcohol up to 20% has, however, no effect on the end-point or on the nature of the curves. In the vicinity of the end-point, the sol begins to coagulate and the equivalence point can be visually detected by the coagulation point of mercury molybdate. The reverse titrations (Fig. 2) provide more concordant and accurate results than the direct titrations (Fig. 1). The jump in potential is more marked in the reverse case. Reverse titrations may be recommended for the potentiometric estimation of Hg^{II} as mercury molybdate in highly acidic medium (pH 1.4 to 2).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The analytical work on the composition of mercury molybdate is under investigation and the results would be communicated shortly.

Thanks are due to Dr. S. Ghosh, D.Sc., F.R.I.C., F.N.I., Head of the Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, for his kind help.